

Simultaneous Quantitative Determination of Metronidazole and Di-iodohydroxyquinoline in Tablet Preparations by Difference Spectrophotometry

P. PARIMOO*, P. UMAPATHI and R. PRABHU**

Department of Pharmacy, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani-333 031

Manuscript received 3 December 1992, revised 23 September 1993, accepted 3 November 1993

A difference spectrophotometric procedure has been developed for the simultaneous quantitation of metronidazole (MND) and di-iodohydroxyquinoline (DIHQ) in tablets. The method involves the measurement of absorbance of a solution of the tablet extract in pH 2.0 buffer solution relative to that of an equimolar solution in pH 13.0 buffer at the wavelengths of 279 and 300 nm. The compliance of Beer's law is obtained in the concentration range 5–30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for MND and 5–15 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for DIHQ.

A combination of MND and DIHQ in the form of tablet preparation is widely used for symptomatic intestinal amoebiasis and hepatic amoebiasis¹. MND is 2-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazol-1-yl)ethanol and DIHQ is 5,7-di-iodoquinolin-8-ol¹. Several methods have been reported for the assay of MND^{2,4} and DIHQ^{3,4}. The Official Monographs describe only the procedure for individual assay of MND and DIHQ^{3,4} and not the procedure for their simultaneous determination in the presence of each other. The present research describes the pH induced difference spectrophotometric method⁵ for the simultaneous quantitation of MND and DIHQ in the presence of each other as well as the excipients.

Results and Discussion

The difference absorption spectrum of solution of MND in pH 2.0 buffer in the reference cell and an equimolar solution of MND in pH 13.0 buffer in the sample cell compartment showed a maximum value of δA (absorbance difference) at 325 nm and a minimum value at 275 nm. Isosbestic point (a wavelength of zero δA due to equal absorptivities of the two species) occurred at 300 nm. The difference absorption spectrum

of solution of DIHQ showed a maximum value of δA at 290 nm and minimum value at 270 nm. Isosbestic points of the DIHQ spectrum were obtained at 260 and 279 nm.

The wavelength of 279 nm was chosen for the estimation of MND since the δA value of MND difference spectrum was more optimal for accurate measurement (≈ 0.35) than the value at 260 nm for the concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The wavelength of 300 nm which was the isosbestic point of MND, was chosen for the quantitation of DIHQ. The absorbance value of DIHQ difference spectra was about 0.200 at 300 nm for a concentration of 13 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. These concentrations were chosen on the basis of the proportion of MND and DIHQ in commercial formulations as well as to have absorbance values between 0.2–1.2 which would provide a minimum relative error⁶.

The absorbances of the solutions of the pure MND, DIHQ and their mixture in pH 2.0 and 13.0 buffers were monitored spectrophotometrically and were found to vary by ± 0.004 AU over a period of one hour.

**Present Address : Department of Pharmaceutics, College of Pharmacy, University of Georgia, Athens, GA 30602, U.S.A.

The regression analysis of the δA values obtained for pure MND ($5-30 \mu\text{g}^{-1}$) and pure DIHQ ($5-15 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) by the least-square method gave regression equations with negligible intercepts and correlation coefficient value of 0.9995. Similarly, the two series of mixtures of MND and DIHQ (mentioned under standard solutions) gave regression equations with negligible intercepts and correlation coefficients of 0.9999 and 0.9998 for the first and second series respectively. The high correlation coefficient values in the order of 0.99 in the case of pure drugs as well as their mixtures indicate the strong positive correlation between the concentration of the drug and the δA values and hence the rectilinearity of the method. The absorbance values of the two series of solutions of drug mixtures are given in Table 1 and the assay results of the commercial formulations by the proposed method in Table 2. The low standard deviation values associated with the measurement of δA of drug mixtures indicate the precision as well as the non-interference of one drug in the absorption measurement of the other.

$$C_{\text{MND}} = \frac{\delta A_{279}^{\text{sam}} C_{\text{MND}}^{\text{std}} \times \text{AW} \times 100}{\delta A_{279}^{\text{std}} W_{\text{t sam}} C_{\text{t}}}$$

$$C_{\text{DIHQ}} = \frac{\delta A_{300}^{\text{sam}} C_{\text{DIHQ}}^{\text{std}} \times \text{AW} \times 100}{\delta A_{300}^{\text{std}} W_{\text{t sam}} C_{\text{t}}}$$

where the concentrations of the standard solutions were in mg ml^{-1} , $W_{\text{t sam}}$ was the weight of tablet powder (mg ml^{-1}) taken for the preparation of sample solution and the weights were in milligram.

TABLE 2—ASSAY RESULTS OF METRONIDAZOLE AND DI-iodohydroxyquinoline IN COMMERCIAL FORMULATIONS BY DIFFERENCE SPECTROSCOPY

Sample	MND (mg/tab)		DIHQ	
	Recovered (mg/tab)	Mean recovery (%)*	Recovered (mg/tab)	Mean recovery (%)*
Brand A	249.65	99.86 ± 0.3361	322.70	99.30 ± 0.3420
Brand B	249.30	99.72 ± 0.3114	322.70	99.30 ± 0.4301
Brand C	249.45	99.78 ± 0.3033	324.60	99.90 ± 0.2863
Brand D	248.95	99.58 ± 0.3420	325.32	100.01 ± 0.3162

*Mean of five replicate measurements, assay as percentage of label claim.

TABLE 1—SELECTIVITY OF THE METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF METRONIDAZOLE AND DI-iodohydroxyquinoline BY DIFFERENCE SPECTROSCOPY

Composition of mixture ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)		Mean (δA) [*] limit	95% Confidence ^{**} limit
MND	DIHQ		
10	13	0.427 ± 0.0033	± 0.0023
15	13	0.638 ± 0.0038	± 0.0027
20	13	0.850 ± 0.0043	± 0.0031
25	13	1.069 ± 0.0051	± 0.0036
30	13	1.270 ± 0.0046	± 0.0033
10	07	0.102 ± 0.0045	± 0.0032
10	09	0.129 ± 0.0055	± 0.0039
10	11	0.159 ± 0.0041	± 0.0029
10	13	0.190 ± 0.0038	± 0.0027
10	15	0.220 ± 0.0047	± 0.0034

*Average of ten replicate measurements. **Based on student's *t* distribution.

The concentration of MND (C_{MND}) and DIHQ (C_{DIHQ}) in the tablet contents of average weight (AW) as a percentage of stated quantity of drug (C_{t}) were calculated using equations,

In the absence of an Official Method for simultaneous determination of MND and DIHQ, the proposed method is found suitable for the simultaneous determination of the components in tablet formulations.

Experimental

The stock solution of MND was prepared by dissolving pure MND (100 mg) in dimethylformamide (DMF) (100 ml). Appropriate volumes of aliquots of the stock solution were made up to 50 ml with pH 2.0 buffer and pH 13.0 buffer separately to give a series of equimolar solutions buffer containing $5-30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of MND. The stock solution of DIHQ was prepared similarly containing $5-15 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of DIHQ. Similarly, two series of 50 ml each of equimolar solution of mixtures of MND and DIHQ in pH 2.0 and pH 13.0 buffers were prepared by using the stock solutions. The first series contained a constant concentration of DIHQ ($15 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and a varying concentration of MND ($5-30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The second

series contained a constant concentration of MND ($10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and a varying concentration of DIHQ ($5\text{--}15 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)

Sample preparation Twenty tablets (of each brand, accurately weighed) were powdered and a weight of the powder equivalent to 50 mg of MND (and 65 mg of DIHQ) was dissolved in DMF (50 ml) and the volume made upto 50 ml. The extract was filtered. The first and the last 5 ml of the filtrate were discarded. The sample solutions of 50 ml of each in pH 2.0 buffer and pH 13.0 buffer were prepared by using 10 ml aliquots of the filtrate so as to obtain equimolar solutions containing approximately 10 of MND and $13 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of DIHQ respectively.

The absorbances of the acidic standard and sample solutions relative to the equimolar pH 13.0 buffer solutions were measured from 250 to 420 nm with a Jasco 7800 spectrophotometer, and the absorbance difference, if any, at the wavelenghts of 279 and 300 nm of the analytes in pH 13.0 buffer solution relative to pH 2.0 buffer were corrected.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Messrs Eskayef Ltd, Mysore, and Messrs Rhone-Poulenc (India) Ltd, Bombay, for the gift sample of pure metronidazole and to Messrs Searle (India) Ltd, Bombay, for the gift samples of pure metronidazole and di-iodohydroxyquinoline.

References

- 1 MARTINDALE, The Extra Pharmacopocia, 29th ed, The Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1989 pp 662-666
- 2 M A BROOKS, L D ARCONTE, and J A F DE SILVA, *J Pharm Sci*, 1976, **65** 112, P PARIMOO *Indian J Pharm Sci*, 1986 **48** 186 *J Indian Chem Soc* 1988 **65** 151, R A MARQUES, B STAFFORD, N FLYNN and W SADFE, *J Chromatogr Biomed Appl* 1978 **146** 163
- 3 L BERGGREN and O HASSON *Clun Pharmac Ther*, 1968 **9** 67
- 4 The United States Pharmacopocia XXII, United States Pharmacopoeial Convention Rockville 1990, Vol XXII p 892, The Pharmacopocia of India, 3rd ed, Government of India, New Delhi 1985 Vol I pp 173, 320
- 5 T D DOYL and F R FEZZARI *J Pharm Sci*, 1974, **63** 1921
- 6 K A CONNORS, A Textbook of Pharmaceutical Analysis 3rd, ed Wiley, New York 1982 pp 195-196

